

Analysis of Managerial Model Principals Elementary School in Medan (Perspective Student Character in Islamic Studies)

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ABSTRACT

The management of education in the school unit always develops according to the needs of the Stake holder. In this study it revealed how to managerial the headmaster in improving the character of students in the Elementary School of Medan. Management of how to implement the school principal by implementing an educational ecosystem that creates culture and climate work, sets the school's physical environment comfortable, beautiful and clean, cultivates an efficient, creative, and Innovative. For updates reach the goal of improving the character of honest students, caring, queuing, confident, and disciplined. As an education that is cultured quality character and qualified. The managerial Model of the principal is very influential to improve the character of students, with the implementation of consistent programs, habituation of good daily, morning talk activities, thematic Qur'an, motivation and the example of the teacher.

Keywords: Model, Managerial Principal, Student Character

INTRODUCTION

The prosperity of a nation is seen with the quality of human resources. Qualified human resources are able to bring a change of nation towards a more positive, every citizen must be able to develop well. The headmaster has a major role in

education, with the aim of developing learners, educating, teaching, guiding, and directing to create students who have character because of the development of citizens not only in terms of Intellectual property, but also in terms of attitudes and skills.

Hendarman and Rohanim (2018:31) Declaring managerial principals can be an inerting education ecosystem that creates a comfortable school culture, guides and develops students ' ability to achieve a teaching learning atmosphere that character, so as to be able to produce a satisfactory quality of education, because the quality of teaching learning that occurs in the school is determined from the majority of the managerial quality of the school principal.

The management of the school principal, of course, every school citizen is able to become a quality human resources that are qualified, able to compete to follow the development of science and technology. School is a means of education in hopes of delivering students who are able to face the changing times. The development of education related to various factors affecting student success, one of students ' compliance with legal programs and school rules, progressive policy of managerial principals of the headmaster is able to create a culture As well as the responsibility of physically organizing the school that is comfortable for students ' learning.

Suyadi (2013:04) stated that character education is an education that

infuses habituation of good things so that the learners understand which is good and which is wrong, good character will be a foothold in the Character education, students who have character will be the driver of the birth of good Children (Insan Kamil). Honest character, caring, confident, culture queueing, and discipline are the characters that students and school residents must have, grow and develop good character encourages students to be Insan Kamil who has a kafasitas and commitment Do everything right and have a purpose of life.

Enhancing the good character in students in need of a system of managerial systems, the chief managerial model creates a culture of working climate conducive to students ' learning, understanding, sensing, experiencing, and practicing values Virtue (moral). Thus the creation of learners who love truth, potentially in the physical, intellectual, emotional, social and spiritual aspects, according to the stage of development as well as the characteristics of the physical environment and the socio-cultural environment in which he lives.

The achievement of 5 characters which is applied incorrectly to the primary school of the city of Medan is one of SD Panca Budi Medan with honest attitude, caring, queueing, confident, and disciplined, various programs in the form for the application of improving the character of students, as intended The education of Medan city is creating learners who are character and Berakhlakul Karimah, noble character includes about the goodness that raises commitment to goodness that ultimately really do good and righteousness.

Character habituation that is applied is a shared responsibility, both school management, teachers, and parents. Thus bringing together a culture of good cooperation in achieving the objectives, making students who are cultured characters and become the driving force of good children, Insan Kamil, have a kafasitas and commitment to do everything right and have a purpose of life. Managerial principals

Create a school's physical environment culture that is comfortable, clean, healthy, cultivating a good working culture, can support improving the character and skills of students who are Berakhlakul Karimah. Producing graduates who are characteristic and quality.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Managerial Model of the principal

A model is a conceptual planning pattern or framework that is used as a guideline in use to create or achieve goals and improve the quality of learners, the model referred to here is the model of the school principal in creating Students who excel in character and the achievement of the student Kamil. (Mahmud Ahmad 2013:56).

Kompri (2017:40) expressed managerial or often called a managers is a highly necessary skill for every leader. It is therefore a person who is tasked with organizing, controlling, directing and responsible for achieving a predetermined planning goal. A manager or principal is essentially a plan manager, organizer, leader, and Controller. The existence of managers on an organization is indispensable, because the organization is a place to build and develop human resources potential, requiring managers who are able to lead, controlling to achieve an effective and efficient objectives.

The headmaster is not only related to the achievement manager, but the competence that can anticipate, to grow and to maintain in the era of higher education competition, able to analyze and predict the situation of the Ahead for a better change for the education world. A manager must have relevant managerial and leadership competencies. Having high emotional and spritual competence to wisely realize the objectives that are well-desired, possess professional traits and values, optimism, integrity, care, humble, and cooperation. (Kompri 2017:36)

A competent manager moves, and takes decisions with its policy

considerations, has a strong organizational commitment to the achievements that have been made, and of course a manager should be able to Leads to the attitude and development of abilities of the team can be in the spirit of leadership as well, and in fact the manager is an agent of change in the system of education institutions.

Scope of Managerial competence

Wirawan (2013:551) States some of the scope of managerial competencies: (1) able to develop school planning for various levels of planning; (2) able to develop the school organization according to the needs; (3) able to pin teachers and staff in order to optimally utilization of manusi resources; (4) Able to manage teachers and staff in the framework of optimal utilization of human resources; (5) Manage the development of curriculum and activities in accordance with the direction and objectives of national education; 6 Able to manage school administration in support of school activities; (7) Able to create a culture and a working climate conducive to students ' learning, etc.

The school chief's managerial competence is able to create a conducive culture and working climate. Working climate is a distinguishing personality with other institutions, managerial principals must have a human working climate, which is participatory according to his leadership style. Working climate is important to be created because it is a picture of the quality of the atmosphere and character with a good working climate will be a motivation for the school to behave in character: (1) able to organize the physical environment of the school Create a comfortable, clean and beautiful atmosphere: (2) able to foster an efficient working culture, creative, innovative, and excellent service oriented.

Principal

The headmaster is a teacher who has the ability to lead all the resources in the school, so that it can be used to the fullest to achieve common goals. As the leader of a

headmaster institution, it is always to develop a harmonious cooperation relationship with the community in order to realize an effective and efficient school.

Furthermore, the understanding of the leader in Islamic perspective, leadership is one of the very important aspects among Islam is seen from so many evidence explaining the leadership, because the leader is one of the factors that For the life of a society. Evidence of leadership (QS. Al-Baqarah 2:30).

وَإِذْ قَالَ رَبُّكَ لِلْمَلَائِكَةِ إِنِّي جَاعِلٌ فِي الْأَرْضِ خَلِيفَةً

"Remember when your Lord said to the angel, verily I will make a caliph on the Earth".

The headmaster is one of the most important educational components in improving the quality of education. Managerial principals create a culture of working climate conducive to students ' learning. So that the headmaster is able to organize a comfortable, clean and beautiful school, forming a healthy atmosphere, and harmonious working relationship.

The success of an institution depends on its leader, the principal as a manager must optimally become spearheaded, creating a learning process capable of driving various learning resources, achieving appropriate learning Vision and mission of the school. Hendarman and the Rohanim (2018:01). So that it can create students with character and quality. Leading the implementation of management activities and evaluating, the headmaster is a person entrusted to mobilize and direct the change to make changes continuously to improve the education of the nation.

The headmaster is an important figure in the training of education in schools not only in the demand to perform tasks in the field of learning, but also in the demand to perform the role of education Unit leader. There are 9 pillars of the role of the principal as follows: (1) as Executive; (2) Planner; (3) an expert (Exspert); (4) Supervise the relationship between the members (Controller of relationship); (5)

representing the group (Group Representativo); Sepetri acts of reward; (6) Act as referees and arbiters (arbitrator and mediator); (7) Holders of responsibility; (8) as a creator (ideological); (9) As a father, (father figure). Juliana (2016:16).

A role that is so complex a school principal should have a high standard of competence to more easily perform his role as a leader in the institution he manages. Well-competent principals will produce and create a working climate conducive to students' learning, creating a motivating culture for students as well as school citizens.

Student Character

Zubaedi (2011:67) states that the character is a system of belief and habit that directs the actions of an individual. Characters are habits, which are already attached to each person and make themselves acting according to their habits. A person is also very important to know whether the action is able to bring good to himself or others or even harm. It is necessary to know the knowledge and habituation to the creation of learners who are character, honest, disciplined, caring, culture queueing, and confident.

Students are one human component that occupies a central position in the learning process, students who aim and want to achieve them optimally, students become the deciding factor to achieve their learning goals. Sumasono (2012:13) stated that the students were children who were schooled to develop themselves following the direction of the education process chosen to be able to develop themselves with their potential. Based on the explanation above that the character of the student is the one who designates good values in the habit or behavior of a student, manifested in the relationship between human beings in daily life.

Character Education Objectives

The most fundamental goal of education is to make a person a good smart.

"Rasulullah SAW asserted that the main mission in Educating man is to seek the establishment of a good character. Moral or character is an inevitable goal of the world of education. Intelligence plus character, that is the true aim of education. Abdul Majid (2010:29). Intelligence plus character that is the correct purpose of education.

The purpose of making man good, and accustomed to doing good. The purpose of education and training can give birth to behavior as a habit of deeds arising from the morality of the deed as a delight for those who do. Forming a believer, noble, advanced and Independent that has a high spiritual resistance and able to adapt to the dynamics of community development. The character education in the perspective of Islamic religion in Indonesia is so that one is accustomed to doing good deeds, strengthening human interaction with Allah Almighty and other creatures, and always well maintained harmoniously.

RESULTS

The desire to achieve a goal is strongly needed a consistent system and regulation, where by regulation will be able to support the realization of a purpose that is desired. If the regulation is observed and carried out in every day, then there is a habit that is carried out by all members concerned so that the creation of a culture that will be characteristic of an organization.

A positive school culture is the heart of change and growth in students' learning. The managerial Model of the headmaster runs the programs that have been established, with a consistent system and habituation that is applied greatly to the achievement of a goal that makes students honest, caring, queueing, confident, and Discipline. Competencies that are able to anticipate to grow and maintain higher educational competition.

The operational standard of the procedure is a guideline for the school that implements the character with a managerial model of the principal is mandatory to be implemented by all elements of the school

unit. Education in the city of Medan to be a base of changing generations to increase the character of human resources, of course in each unit of elementary school performs synergically with the entire stake holder, both teachers, students and parents of students. This is one of them can be seen in SD Panca Budi Medan which has made an integrated system, able to support the achievement of a value that is desired, because it is supported by the implementation Manual in which aspects 5 characters honest, caring, queued, Confident, and disciplined. Good habituation including familiarizing life with Qur'anic character and soul, the principal is very important to be able to direct its members to comply with the rules and implement the program that has been made.

The achievement of five characters through habituation activities in the morning until after school, the achievement of five characters is a responsibility with the management, teachers, and parents of students, to support the achievement of five characters, then Habituation in school in doing consistently and good cooperation. Management of all teachers and parents is a Role model for students, the entire process of implementing and five-character achievement will be evaluated and shared. The systems' managerial Model is very significant in enhancing the character of students.

Honesty of students is one of the character values that will be accomplished, making procedures and programs that will encourage the achievement of students who have honest character in themselves, God, and others. School management has prepared a box of honesty that will support children to behave honestly.

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا اتَّقُوا اللَّهَ وَفُؤُلُوا قَوْلًا سَدِيدًا يُصْلِحْ لَكُمْ أَعْمَالَكُمْ وَيَغْفِرْ لَكُمْ ذُنُوبَكُمْ وَمَنْ يُطِيعِ اللَّهَ وَرَسُولَهُ فَقَدْ فَازَ فَوْزًا عَظِيمًا ﴿٧١﴾

"Hi those who believe in Allah, and bless you with the right words, Allah will improve your charity and forgive your sins, and

whoever obeyed God and His messenger, then he is in a great victory"

A system of managerial systems that are capable of creating a working culture and a working climate. Foster an efficient, creative, and innovative workplace culture. Very support to create a comfortable school culture. Cooperation is not only between the headmaster and the teacher, but the school is actually like "triangle", which is school, teacher, and parents, this triangle must go well in achieving the maximum goal, these three elements that we will embrace in Achievement of objectives, when the third is optimal it will succeed a basic education. The following findings on the image of the cooperation model of SD Panca Budi Medan.

The cooperation that is planted is open, mutual embrace, work according to Jobdesc each, and strive to be a team, because basically humans can not live alone, with a triangular working model between the school principal, teachers, and parents will Supports the achievement of students in the character culture both in school and outside school, thus bringing together satisfactory cooperation and quality.

Students' concern is the universal values of human behaviour, moral traits of morality, habits, behaviors, which include inner nature, influencing all minds, which become the individual habit of a human being, inherent habits or habit Human beings, acting according to the habits and factors of his own life. Caring attitude is explained in (QS. Ali Imran 4:104).

وَلَتَكُنْ مِنْكُمْ أُمَّةٌ يَدْعُونَ إِلَى الْخَيْرِ وَيَأْمُرُونَ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَيَنْهَوْنَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ وَأُولَئِكَ هُمُ الْمُفْلِحُونَ ﴿١٠٤﴾

And there shall be among you an ummah who attacks the virtue, telling the Ma'ruf and preventing it from the possibility of those who are fortunate.

Confident is the attitude that must be applied in the educational world, this is one form of courage students in acting and committed in determining the choice, confident is a good moral form, the character that will be the footing In

everyday life that has a kafa'iyah do everything right and have a purpose of life. Confident is the attitude relating to the nature and attitude of a believer who has a positive value in him and has a strong belief to do, choose, perform, also other activities. Confident attitude is so important in the world of education, it is explained in the Qur'an.

وَلَا تَهِنُوا وَلَا تَحْزَنُوا وَأَنْتُمْ الْأَعْلَوْنَ إِنْ كُنْتُمْ مُؤْمِنِينَ ﴿١٣٩﴾

Do not be weak, nor do you grieve, but you are the most high (the degree) if you are believers (QS. Ali Imran 4:139).

Environmental factors are very much a big influence in the education of children's character, the good environment will support the creation of good character in the child, as well as the opposite of an environment that is not good or not good will be able to bring no good influence to the child. This suggests the planting of moral value from an early age.

A teacher must always give advice to the participants. Aside from being a teacher, teachers are also educators. Giving advice is one of the good habits that we should keep. The advice that gives can be a moral message of morality, personality problems, social relations and life. However, it should be noted and sought to give this counsel not to be impressed or to block them. Therefore teachers must have the skills to advise students gently. (Sukadi 2006:139).

Elementary school education in an environment in the city of Medan one of the schools that apply a managerial model of the headmaster in improving the character of the student one of them in the findings is SD Panca Budi Medan, which is able to implement a good habituation of 5 characters Students i.e. (1) Honesty;(2) care; (3) queued; (4) Confident; (5) and the discipline in which it looks good is the students ' awareness of habituation that is applied daily, judging by the discipline of students who are too late in decline, honest with themselves and return the non-rights, confident also Very visible to many learners

who want to appear fore both school events are also outside school, the concerned very spontaneity appears when there are people who are affected by the accident or adversity. The achievement of 5 characters has been continuity between the managerial model of the principal, good working culture, available facilities, and a consistent daily habituation program able to assist in enhancing the character of students, so that the learners Able to have good character culture in school or outside school.

CONCLUSION

The managerial model of the headmaster in enhancing the character of students is an open system model, creating a climate and working culture, by setting up a comfortable, clean and beautiful school's physical environment, cultivating an efficient, creative, and Innovative. Managerial ranging from digging the teacher's character data and how it approaches, determination, qualification development, and work programs, target determination, good cooperation, Mission Vision Alignment, Jobdesc division, and maintenance stages regarding rewards and Punishment, a system and a commitment. A managerial model of the principal with an open system model is influential in improving the character of honest, caring, queued, confident, and disciplined students with consistent programs, through habituation well before starting Learning until completion, Morning Talk, the Qur'an thematic, and the motivation and the example of teachers, able to create students culture and good character.

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